

Open Science Guide

Advancing Open Science: RDM & FAIR Training Framework for RPOs

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Executive Summary

The research ecosystem is undergoing a transformation driven by digital advancements, artificial intelligence, emerging technologies, and Open Science. Conducting excellent research requires using new research infrastructures, services and software as well as the adoption of new skills. This technological shift emphasises the need to recognise that, in the 21st century, groundbreaking research is based on the interplay between technology and the expertise of the project team – including researchers, support staff, and emerging professions such as data stewards.

This Guide addresses the growing need for upskilling across diverse roles within Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), ensuring effective engagement with Open Science and FAIR enabling infrastructures, services and practices. It supports the RPOs in addressing training needs by providing a framework for developing targeted training programs. Training needs, naturally, vary widely depending on the various roles within the institution (administration, research support, or scientific personnel), different career stages (students, early-career researchers, senior researchers), and scientific discipline. The guide outlines the best practices for designing and implementing tailored training initiatives, within the specific context of the RPOs and their organisational cultures. The actions include:

- **Map Roles and Required Skills** – Identify key Research Data Management (RDM)-related roles, their responsibilities, and necessary competencies, ensuring staff flexibility to adapt to technological and policy changes.
- **Identify Training Needs** – Conduct a structured Training Needs Assessment (TNA) to align training initiatives with organisational goals and employee development.
- **Develop and Deliver Training** – Design training programmes tailored to diverse roles and responsibilities, leveraging both formal and informal learning approaches.
- **Implement Open Science in Curricula** – Integrate Open Science and FAIR principles into student education to build responsible research practices and enhance interdisciplinary collaboration.
- **Evaluate Training Outcomes** – Assess training effectiveness through knowledge assessments, performance metrics, and feedback mechanisms.
- **Sustain Learning Culture** – Encourage professional development by providing recognition, rewards, and opportunities for upskilling within a supportive institutional framework.
- **Share Educational Resources** – Ensure training materials are accessible and long-term available, promoting FAIR-by-Design principles for learning resources.

Introduction

Researchers today operate in a digital world supported by artificial intelligence (AI) and research infrastructures (RIs). With high-quality data, ground breaking research can provide answers to numerous societal challenges, addressing global and local issues with innovative solutions. Trustworthy science, research integrity, and research excellence are at the heart of modern scientific progress. However, without effective research data management (RDM) and Open Science, maintaining these core principles becomes increasingly difficult. These practices benefit both researchers and institutions. Open data sharing increases the chances of data citation, enhancing the visibility of researchers and their contributions. Registering research results in data repositories enables global identification of scientists and their achievements while also fostering collaboration between research teams nationally and internationally, thereby increasing research efficiency.

A transparent research process is fundamental to credibility and learning from past successes and mistakes. Open Science maximises data use, reducing research time and costs while reinforcing accountability and public trust in scientific findings. Effective data management supports the entire research cycle, enabling risk assessment and mitigation, including data storage and loss prevention. Open data empower young scientists, PhD students, and citizen scientists to conduct research using available, high-quality datasets and publish their findings, even without grants. They also foster interdisciplinary collaboration, leading to new insights across scientific fields. Additionally, effective research data management is essential for commercialising findings and collaborating with businesses. By driving innovation, open data strengthen cross-sector partnerships and enhance the economic and societal impact of research.

As a result, data management requirements are increasingly embedded in institutional policies, research funding regulations (e.g., ERC, Horizon Europe), and university Open Science strategies. Scientific publishers also play a key role, with many journals mandating open data sharing to enhance transparency and research quality.

The adoption of new skills and the training of personnel to become informed users as well as providers of emerging technologies is essential. Additionally, new and more flexible forms of collaboration, while ensuring a clear division of roles within research teams—such as researcher, Principal Investigator (PI), Data Steward, or software engineer—are key to adapting to the evolving dynamics of modern research.

The European Open Science Cloud ([EOSC](#)) plays a key role in the transition to Open Science. It supports researchers in storing, sharing, processing, analysing, and using Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) research outputs on a European level. In the current build-up phase of the EOSC Federation, the [EOSC EU Node](#) has been established, already providing access to services, computing and data resources. Moreover, this process aligns with the deployment of

national and thematic EOSC nodes and the European Data Spaces. Scientific discovery is thus encouraged at many levels, but this also creates a high demand for skills and training.

Building a Strong RDM Training Framework for Organisations

The evolving research ecosystem requires RPOs to provide training programmes designed to meet specific scientific needs and develop digital and Open Science skills. This enables the effective use of research infrastructures and services, and the production of high-quality, FAIR research data in line with standards. These capabilities are fundamental for excellent research and maintaining research integrity. However, the growing need for upskilling is diverse, depending on one’s placement within organisational structures (administration, research support or scientific personnel), career stage (e.g., students, senior researchers), and scientific domain, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Data Professional Roles with MVS. Source: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006581>

While shaping a response to the upskilling demand, the RPOs need to acknowledge that the one-size-fit-all approach does not exist. The training framework needs to reflect on the needs of the organisation, its employees, and on the thorough assessment of existing skills and training needs.

The Significance of Open Science Roles in RPOs

Collaborative efforts between researchers, research support staff and emerging new profiles - such as data stewards, research software engineers and next-generation lab technicians - play a critical role in facilitating RDM and transition to Open Science practices.

A combined approach, where these highly qualified professionals possess domain-specific knowledge, while scientists acquire foundational expertise in RDM, will enable institutions to foster communication and efficiency in addressing the technical, legal, and organisational challenges of an increasingly data-driven environment.

RDM is a cross-cutting and comprehensive process that reflects the entire data lifecycle. At its core is the collaboration between scientists, who bring domain-specific expertise, and data stewards, who provide the necessary technical capabilities. However, the effective implementation of RDM extends beyond these roles. It is crucial to acknowledge the contributions of other experts within the RPOs is a critical element, for example legal advisors offer expertise in data legislation and intellectual property rights (IPR).

Data Stewards

Data stewards are key professionals responsible for implementing RDM practices and FAIR principles across all stages of the research data cycle, from supporting the creation of a Data Management Plan to data sharing and long-term preservation. They ensure compliance with standards, legal and regulatory frameworks, and support researchers in adopting domain-specific best practices. Beyond operational support, data stewards may also contribute significantly to capacity building by developing RDM curricula, design course content, and deliver training sessions. They ensure that the research practice aligns with OS institutional policies, national guidelines, and discipline-specific needs.

Figure 2. Booklet Data Steward: Minimum Viable Skills Profile. Source: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006764>

A critical element of this training framework is the integration of Open Science roles within RPOs, particularly the collaboration between researchers, research support staff, and emerging professionals such as data stewards. These roles are pivotal in facilitating RDM and the transition to Open Science practices. A combined approach—where data stewards bring domain-specific expertise and scientists acquire foundational RDM knowledge—fosters communication and institutional efficiency in managing technical, legal, and organisational challenges.

Action Points

Map Roles and Required Skills

Given that RPOs vary in their structural and thematic scope, each institution must conduct its own mapping exercise to identify key actors in RDM and clarify their roles, goals and required skills set. This tailored approach ensures that RDM strategies align with institutional needs.

Staff responsible must have the appropriate awareness, knowledge and skills to handle their roles effectively. Moreover, it is crucial to foster flexibility by enabling staff to adapt to new digital developments and update their expertise and build learning communities and networks. Competence flexibility ensures that the institution remains agile and responsive to the evolving landscape of Open Science, advancements in technology, changing policies, and emerging best practices.

Steps

1. Conduct mapping of RDM-related roles in your organisation.
 - a. Identify roles that contribute to RDM;
 - b. Define at which stages of the data lifecycle these roles contribute;
 - c. Break down the core responsibilities and key deliverables of each role;
 - d. Consider cross-domain and domain-specific needs.
2. Analyse skills requirements and identify the MVS for each identified RDM role in your organisation.
 - a. Technical skills (e.g., data collection methods, data curation method, data analysis, coding)
 - b. Soft skills (e.g., communication, problem-solving, teamwork, sensitive approach)
 - c. Data-specific knowledge (e.g., FAIR, CARE and TRUST standards, ethics guidelines, regulations, safety procedures; security policies, PID policies, legal aspects of data)

Tools (examples)

Job Task Analysis (JTA), Skill Mapping; Benchmarking Against Standards, Interviews, Focus groups, Expert panels, and Advisory committees.

Identify Training Needs

Scope

Training Needs Assessment (TNA) is a structured process to identify skill gaps, performance issues, and learning needs within an organisation. It ensures that training efforts align with organisational goals and employee development and reach all relevant stakeholders.

Align training with employee skill gaps focusing on the organisational needs in the area of data management.

Steps

1. Identify Open Science/RDM Policy Goals and KPIs for Open Science/RDM
 - a. Define Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for skills required to achieve the organisation's Open Science and RDM policy goals.
2. Assess the performance gap in RDM.
3. Assess skills gap in RDM.
4. Align training with gaps to ensure that training addresses recognised skills and performance gaps.
5. Define learning paths with a set of training objectives to enable career development pathways for RDM professionals.

Tools (examples)

Surveys, Interviews, Focus groups, Performance reviews, SMART.

Provide Training for Staff

Scope

A well-designed and effectively delivered training programme, considering the diversity of roles and responsibilities, is crucial for ensuring the effectiveness of the learning process. RPOs have different organisational models. It means that unique structures and needs should be considered (i.e., if there is an RDM/Open Science competence or training centre or an Open Science Coordinator). It also requires a sensitive approach towards the domain-specific character of research data.

Steps

1. Consider different areas of RDM and Open Science expertise, such as:
 - a. Introduction to concepts: Open Science, RDM, FAIR, CARE

- b. Research Data: Metadata, Data Lifecycle, Data Workflow, Research Data Management
- c. Data Management Plan (including concept of machine-actionability)
- d. The FAIR principles (including controlled vocabularies, persistent identifiers)
- e. Reuse of Research Data (including interoperability issues, file formats, legal aspects)
- f. Reproducible Research and Data Analysis
- g. Data Infrastructures and Collaborative Platforms (including repositories, Virtual Research Environments, Electronic Lab Notebooks)
- h. ELSI - Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues (including access, encryption, security)
- i. Open Peer Review Metrics and Evaluation
- j. Cybersecurity
- k. Science Communication and Citizen Science
- l. Open Educational Resources

Examples for Training Concepts

- [Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management](#) (English 2024)
- [Train-the-Trainer Konzept zum Thema Forschungsdatenmanagement](#) (original German version 2023)

2. Define roles and responsibilities for delivering training in the organisation. Assign responsibilities to the dedicated team/unit or individuals (e.g., Open Science Coordinators) to ensure high-quality delivery.
 - a. Assign responsibilities to dedicated teams or units.
 - b. Engage key individuals to ensure high-quality delivery.
3. Determine training features:
 - a. Decide on training format: online, in-person, lectures, in-house training, external training, mixed approaches, etc.
 - b. Establish training methods, incorporating both formal and informal approaches (e.g., on-the-job training, mentoring, peer-to-peer learning).
 - c. Identify trainers, selecting internal and external experts, mentors, and peers.
 - d. Decide on the most appropriate training materials which will help you sustain the knowledge in the organisation (e.g., multimedia presentations, MOOCs, and exercises).
4. Allocate adequate budget resources to cover trainer related expenses (e.g., fees, materials, travel costs, catering, and travel allowances).
 - a. Secure funding sources, identifying internal and external resources.

5. Plan logistics, including venues, equipment, and platforms (e.g., lecture rooms, virtual platforms).
 - a. Provide necessary equipment, such as laptops, and learning management systems (LMS).
6. Promote training opportunities,
 - a. Actively engage ambassadors and mentors.
 - b. Utilise effective institutional communication channels.

Tools

Role mapping, Responsibility matrices or Competency frameworks, Upskilling programs and initiatives, LMS, MOOC, Interactive workshops, case studies, mentorship programs and networks, scheduling software, virtual meeting platforms, budget planning tools, newsletters, engagement campaigns.

Many institutions complement training courses and personalised support with internal guidelines and practical toolkits. Depending on the resources available, these guides often comprise a combination of in-house services and tools, alongside external resources, to support effective data management. Examples of institutional Open Science toolkits can be found below.

Examples of Open Science Toolkits for Researchers

- Open Economics Guide of the ZBW, <https://openeconomics.zbw.eu/en/>
- Open Science Toolbox of the Open Science Centre of the LMU Munich, <https://www.osc.uni-muenchen.de/toolbox/index.html>

Implement Open Science in Students' Curricula

Scope

By teaching Open Science principles early, researchers develop responsible research habits, improve collaboration across disciplines, and contribute to more efficient knowledge dissemination. Moreover, Open Science aligns with the growing demand for publicly funded research to be openly available, increasing societal trust in science. Implementing these principles in research education ensures that future scientists are well-equipped to navigate and contribute to an evolving, more inclusive scientific landscape.

Steps

1. Assess current curriculum and identify gaps
 - a. Review existing research training programmes to determine the extent of Open Science coverage.
2. Develop course content and materials
 - a. Develop introduction courses and/or integrate Open Science principles into existing research methodology courses.
 - b. Create specialized modules on topics like pre-registration, open peer review, and data sharing.
 - c. Include case studies and best practices from real-world Open Science projects.
3. Develop institutional policies and support structures
 - a. Establish guidelines for Open Science adoption within the institution.
 - b. Provide incentives for researchers and students to engage in open practices.
 - c. Ensure ethical considerations and compliance with data protection regulations.
4. Evaluate and Adapt
 - a. Collect feedback from students and faculties on the effectiveness of Open Science training.
 - b. Measure the impact on research quality, collaboration, and visibility.

Evaluate Training Outcomes

Evaluating training outcomes is essential to ensure the effectiveness of knowledge and skills uptake in RDM. A well-structured evaluation process helps assess whether training programs meet their objectives, address domain-specific needs, and support diverse roles, including researchers, data stewards, and research support staff.

Considerations

- Knowledge assessments (tests, quizzes, practical applications)
- Long-term impact evaluation (e.g., performance metrics, feedback from the community)

Tools (examples)

- For post-training feedback: Focus Groups, Interviews, Survey Tools: Survey Monkey, Google
- For peer, supervisor and self-assessment: 360-Degree Feedback Platforms (e.g., Culture Amp, Lattice, Qualtrics)
- For practical applications: Role-Playing, Scenario-Based Assessments, Simulations & Virtual Labs

- For students: Feedback procedure as implemented in the institution

Sustain Learning Culture

Foster a culture of continuous improvement by encouraging staff to regularly update their skills and stay informed about Open Science trends and developments. Provide learning pathways, encouraging, recognising and rewarding professional development and strengthen the learning culture of the organisation.

Steps

1. Recognise upskilling

Tools: Performance reviews & assessments, certifications & badges, competency-based assessments, promotions & career progression, recognition programs & awards, manager & peer feedback; encouraging external recognition.

Data Steward as Career Path

Specialised training for Data Stewards is crucial to bridge the gap between research excellence and technical requirements of RDM. Data Steward as a specific career path enables institutions to recruit from up-and-coming researchers familiar with the research lifecycle. This offers scientific personnel an alternative to a purely academic path while staying involved in research processes. However, it requires providing professional learning and career paths.

- [RDA Interest Group "Professionalising Data Stewardship"](#)
- [RDA Working Group "Data Steward Career Tracks"](#)
- [EOSC-A Task Force "Data Stewardship, Curricula and Career Paths"](#)

2. Reward the upskilling

Tools: financial rewards, career development, recognition & appreciation, work-life benefit, incentives, mentorship, customised rewards.

3. Encourage upskilling

Methods: create an environment for learning/training/upskilling; dedicated time, space and working conditions for upskilling by flexible roles that allow staff to adapt to technological, policy, and institutional changes (e.g., job rotation, cross functional teams). Design flexible roles that allow staff to adapt to technological, policy, and institutional changes; facilitate opportunities for staff to engage with external Open Science networks and communities to help them gain fresh perspectives, share knowledge, and build collaborations.

Tools (examples)

Internal Training Programs, Learning Management Systems (LMS), networking, learning community.

Share Educational Resources

For an enhanced learning culture across institutions, it is important to make training materials accessible and long-term available. Applying a [FAIR-by-Design methodology](#) for learning materials will foster availability and integration.

Useful Resources

Numerous international, European, and national organisations offer diverse learning opportunities in the field of Open Science.

The EU project Skills4EOSC has developed a [Learning Platform](#) that contains Open Science courses for different target groups, such as RDM trainers, policymakers, students and researchers.

The EU project OSCAR provides domain-specific online resources in the form of the Clusters' Open Science Competence Centres ([CLOCCs](#)), which foster research excellence through training and knowledge transfer, and providing expertise, best practices and services in relation to Open Science.

Currently, the EOSC EU Node also provides open training resources. Future EOSC Nodes are encouraged to have general and domain specific training platforms where learning materials are registered and findable.

Training at International and European Level

At the global level, the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) (2021) prioritises investment in training, education, digital literacy to building required human and institutional capacities for Open Science implementation. In order to enhance the implementation of the Recommendation, UNESCO has provided the [Open Science Tool](#), which is a set of resources for the stakeholders.

Since 2016, the European Commission has organised its Open Science policy according to “8 Pillars”, where one of them is “Education and Skills”. It states that “all scientists in Europe should have the necessary skills and support to apply open science research routines and practices.” Many resources have been developed to help build the European research community’s skills and

competences in the areas of Open Access to publications, management of research data, and citizen science.¹

General Training References

- [UNESCO Open Science Capacity Building Index](#)
- [UNESCO Open Science Toolkit](#)
- [OpenPlato](#)
- [OpenAire Community of Practice](#)
- [FOSTER Open Science EU Courses](#)
- [The Carpentries Network](#)
- [Open Science Training Handbook](#)

Training at National Level

National Open Science initiatives are essential for adapting and applying international Open Science training frameworks at the local level. They help ensure that Open Science principles are in harmony with national research priorities, funding mechanisms, and institutional policies. EOOSC Nodes, as envisaged in the [EOOSC Federation Handbook](#), are instrumental in supporting national-level Open Science efforts.

Examples of National Training Platforms

Many countries have established specialised platforms to offer training in Open Science. These platforms typically feature repositories of training materials, certification programs, and national helpdesks to assist with Open Science initiatives.

- [Essentials 4 Data Support Course](#) (Netherlands)
- [Dalia](#) (Germany)
- [SciLifeLab Training Hub, Open Science in the Swedish Context, Course Syllabus](#) (Sweden)
- [MOOC Online Courses on Data Stewardship for Researchers](#) (Poland)

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, O'Carroll, C., Hyllseth, B., Berg, R., et al., "Providing researchers with the skills and competencies they need to practise Open Science," *Publications Office*, 2017, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/121253>

National Data Steward Initiatives

Some countries have implemented national Data Steward initiatives to foster collaboration and exchange of data stewards at a local level. Examples below (non-exhaustive list):

- Austria: [National RDM Exchange](#)
- Belgium: [Flemish Research Data Network \(FRDN\)](#)
- France: [Recherche Data Gouv](#)
- Ireland: [Irish Data Stewardship Network](#)
- Netherlands: [Data Stewards Interest Group](#)
- Portugal: [Portuguese Data Stewards Network](#)
- Sweden: [The SND Network](#)
- Switzerland: [Swiss Research Data Support Network \(SRDSN\)](#)

Accredited Training Programmes

Over the last years, many institutions have started to implement accredited, quality-assessed training programmes for data stewards (train-the-trainer-oriented), but also for bachelor, master and PhD students, some of the running programmes are listed below (non-exhaustive). The goal is to include data expertise in all domains, to raise awareness of technical and legal knowledge as well as project management skills early on, and lastly, to make them an integral part of projects and research activities. Students should be prepared for current and upcoming demands in academia as well as in the job market and help them to ensure competitiveness on an international level.

Accredited Training Programmes for Data Stewards

- [Certificate Course Data Steward](#), University of Vienna (Austria), 15 ECTS, continuing education
- [Certificate Course Research Data Management](#), TH Köln (Germany), 8 ECTS, continuing education
- [Introduction to Research Data Handling](#), KIT (Germany)
- [Research data management](#), CSC (Finland), 1 ECTS, self-study course
- [Introduction to Open Research and the FAIR data Principles](#), DCC (UK)
- [CUAP Data Steward for Open Science](#), UNITO (Italy)

Programmes for Early Career Students

- [Self-study Course Research Data Management](#), CSC (Finland), 1 ECTS, general course for everybody
- [Introduction to Research Data Management](#), TU Wien (Austria), 3 ECTS, for bachelor and master students (PhD students are also accepted)
- [Open Science for Engineers and Researchers](#), Chalmers (Sweden), 7.5 ECTS, for students at an advanced level (both, master students and PhDs, are accepted)

Programmes for PhD Students

- [Catalan universities course on open science](#), Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (Spain), course within the Transferable Skills Training Programme, self-learning mode, for PhD students
- [UC3M Ticket2Open Science](#), UC3M (Spain), 3 ECTS, for PhD students
- [Scholarly Communication in An Open Science Perspective](#), DKB (Denmark), 1 ECTS, for PhD students
- [Scientific work: Publishing and Dissemination](#), TU Wien (Austria), 3 ECTS, for PhD students
- [Research Methodology for Technical Sciences](#), UKIM (North Macedonia), 3 ECTS, for PhD students
- [Data management and open science](#), UMEA University (Sweden), 7.5 ECTS, for PhD students
- [Responsible Conduct of Research](#), SDU (Denmark), 2 ECTS, for PhD students
- [Open Science MOOC](#), TU Delft (Netherlands), 6 weeks á 3-4 hours, for PhD students
- [Open Science Trainings](#), TAU (Finland), The university library offers various courses that includes open science
- [Open Science and Reproducible Research](#), Karolinska Institute (Sweden), 3 ECTS, for PhD students
- [Research Data Management and Open Science](#), PoliTO (Italy), 15 hours, for PhD students
- [Research data management and publishing](#), UT (Estonia), 3 ECTS Open Science (6 in total), for PhD students

Glossary

Term	Definition	What it Does?	Examples
CARE Principles	A set of principles and standards that ensure Collective Benefit, Accountability, Responsibility, and Ethics of data management practices.	<p>The CARE principles stand for:</p> <p>Collective Benefit: Ensuring that data management practices benefit all stakeholders, particularly marginalised or underrepresented groups.</p> <p>Accountability: Holding those involved in data collection, storage, and analysis accountable for their actions, ensuring transparency and fairness.</p> <p>Responsibility: Acknowledging and respecting the rights of those whose data is being managed and used.</p> <p>Ethics: Adopting ethical approaches to data governance that respect privacy, consent, and other rights.</p>	<p>FAIR Data Maturity Model WG</p> <p>The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance</p>
CODAS	Composable Open Data and Analysis Services	Framework that enables users to flexibly create and customise their data analytics experiences by integrating various data sources and analytical tools in a modular fashion.	
CLOCCs	Clusters' Open Science Competence Centres	Community-based virtual hubs dedicated to fostering research excellence through training and knowledge transfer, and providing expertise, best practices and services in relation to Open Science.	Science Clusters OSCARS
Collaborative Platforms	A digital environment that enables individuals, teams, or organisations to communicate, share resources, and work together efficiently, regardless of location.	These platforms provide tools for real-time collaboration, project management, data sharing, and workflow automation.	Repositories, Virtual Research Environments, Electronic Lab Notebooks
Competence Center	A Competence Center (also called a Center of Excellence, CoE) is a dedicated unit or team within an organisation that focuses on developing expertise, best practices, and innovation in a specific domain.	It serves as a hub for knowledge, training, and strategy to improve efficiency and performance across the organisation.	Open Science Competence Center Gdańsk University of Technology

Term	Definition	What it Does?	Examples
Data lifecycle	Refers to the series of stages data goes through from its creation to its eventual disposal. It ensures efficient data management, security, and usability throughout its lifespan	It ensures data quality, security, and compliance; helps organisations optimise storage and processing; supports data governance and decision-making.	
Data Management Plan	Data Management Plan (DMP) is a formal document outlining how data will be collected, stored, organised, shared, and preserved throughout a research project or organisational process.	It ensures data quality, security, and compliance with institutional and legal requirements. It also enhances data integrity and reproducibility. It facilitates collaboration and transparency in research. It is used by funding agencies (e.g., Horizon Europe, NSF, NCN).	DMPonline
Data Steward	A professional responsible for managing, maintaining, and ensuring the quality, security, and governance of data within an organisation. They act as a bridge between the researchers, IT compliance teams to ensure that data is FAIR and CARE.	Promote and implement RDM and FAIR principles across all levels of research.	Embedded data steward Coordinator data steward Data champion
ELSI	Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues		
EOSC (European Open Science Cloud)	A European initiative to provide a digital infrastructure for storing and sharing research data.	Supports researchers with tools, services, and data storage solutions to promote Open Science practices.	EOSC Federation Handbook , EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) , EOSC Skills4EOSC Program .
EOSC Federation Handbook	EOSC Federation Handbook comprehensively address the purpose, structure, governance, architecture and operations of the EOSC Federation.	It serves as a reference document for organisations interested in joining and contributing to the EOSC Federation, outlining the necessary commitments, responsibilities, and procedures.	EOSC Federation Handbook
European Data Spaces	Secure, interoperable environments designed to enable the sharing, access, and exchange of data across different sectors within the European Union while ensuring data sovereignty,	Facilitate seamless data exchange between businesses, governments, and individuals; drive AI, research, and digital transformation; maintain EU control over strategic data; enable compatibility across sectors and countries.	Common European Data Spaces

Term	Definition	What it Does?	Examples
	security, and compliance with EU regulations.		
FAIR	A framework ensuring research data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.	Facilitates data sharing and long-term preservation to enhance research transparency and reproducibility.	GO FAIR Initiative, FAIRsFAIR Policy Recommendations (2021), The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Nature).
Gap Analysis, Priority Matrices	Tools used to assess and prioritise Open Science initiatives.	Gap Analysis: Identifies existing Open Science strengths and weaknesses. - Priority Matrices: Ranks Open Science areas by feasibility and impact.	Focus Groups or Workshops, Gap Analysis, Problem Tree, SWOT, PESTLE, 5C, VRIO, Porter's Five Forces Analysis.
Incentives and Rewards	Rewards are the formal mechanisms used to acknowledge and recognise researchers for their open science efforts. They are typically provided by institutions, funders, or other organisations.	Create an environment that fosters open science, ultimately leading to more transparent, collaborative, and impactful research.	Recommendations on Open Science Rewards and Incentives.
Job Task Analysis (JTA)	A systematic process used to identify and evaluate the specific tasks, skills, knowledge, and abilities required for a particular job.	It identifies and evaluate the specific tasks, skills, knowledge, and abilities required for a particular job.	
KPI	Key Performance Indicators	Is a measurable value that indicates how effectively an individual, team, or organisation is achieving specific goals. KPIs help track progress, guide decision-making, and improve performance.	Time to Productivity – How quickly employees apply new skills in their roles. Training Completion Rate – Percentage of employees who finish the course.
League of European Research Universities (LERU)	A network of research-intensive universities that advocates for Open Science and offers institutional policy recommendations.	Provides guidance on implementing Open Science practices and influences EU policies related to research.	LERU Report on Implementing Open Science.
LMS	Learning Management System	A platform used to create, manage, deliver, and track online learning and training programs.	Moodle (Open-Source, Education); Blackboard Learn

Term	Definition	What it Does?	Examples
			(Higher Education & Enterprises)
MOOC	Massive Open Online Courses	An online educational course designed to be accessible to many learners worldwide. Typically, free or low-cost, making high-quality education available to anyone with an internet connection.	MOOC Online Courses for Data Stewards
MVS	Minimum Viable skillset	MVS are profiles of research data professionals, people whose role includes creating, collecting or using research data.	Minimum Viable Skillsets: A Briefing for Competence Centres
OER	Open Educational Resources		
Open Access		Open Access to Published Research Results	
ODC-ODbL (Open Database License)	A license under Open Data Commons that requires derived works of databases to remain open.	Protects open data by ensuring any modified versions of the dataset are shared openly.	OpenAIRE Research Graph
OLS (Open Life Science Program)	A program supporting the Open Life Science community through training and mentoring to encourage open research practices.	Provides resources and support for researchers to adopt open science practices in their work.	OLS Training Program , open research initiatives.
RDA (Research Data Alliance)	An international organisation that promotes data sharing and management best practices.	Facilitates collaboration on global data sharing initiatives, ensuring data is properly managed and shared.	RDA Recommendations and Outputs .
RDM	Research Data Management	Cross-cutting and comprehensive process that reflects the entire data lifecycle.	RDM at TU Wien
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound (SMART) training objectives		
SRIA	EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda and its Multi-Annual Roadmap.	Defines the general framework for future research, development and innovation activities in relation to the European Open Science Cloud. ¹ It is used to inform the work programmes via the Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR).	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)
SWOT Analysis	A strategic tool for assessing strengths, weaknesses, opportunities,	Provides a structured approach to evaluating frameworks. A SWOT analysis is designed to facilitate a realistic, fact-based, data-driven	

Term	Definition	What it Does?	Examples
	and threats in Open Science initiatives.	look at the strengths and weaknesses of an organisation.	
TNA	Training Needs Assessment	A systematic process used to identify skill gaps, knowledge deficiencies, and training requirements within an organisation or individual workforce. It helps determine what training is needed, who needs it, and how it should be delivered to improve performance and meet organisational goals.	
TRUST Principles	A set of guiding principles to demonstrate digital repository trustworthiness: Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology (TRUST).	Principles the repositories must uphold to earn the trust of the communities they intend to serve and demonstrate that they are reliable and capable of appropriately managing the data they hold.	The TRUST Principles for digital repositories
UNESCO	The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization	Promotes Open Science through policy development, guidelines, and tools to ensure equal access to scientific knowledge.	UNESCO Open Science Toolkit , Software Heritage Initiative
VRE	Virtual Research Environments	An online collaborative platform that provides researchers with the tools, data, computing resources, and communication channels needed to conduct research efficiently. It enables remote collaboration, data sharing, analysis, and visualisation in a secure and integrated digital workspace.	Galaxy, Dataverse